

USE OF “FLIPPED CLASSROOM” TECHNOLOGY IN EFL TEACHING

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The flipped classroom, as a fundamental component of blended learning, is rapidly gaining popularity among researchers and educators. The inverted classroom technology suggests a learning process arrangement in which classroom activities and homework swap positions. The authors report the outcomes of their experience with flipped classroom in the language classroom. The study found that using the mentioned technology in the learning process boosts student motivation and improves academic performance.

Keywords: *Flipped classroom technology; blended learning; e-learning environment; classroom activities; language learning.*

Introduction

Today technological literacy and the desire of the individual to seek knowledge independently are coming to the fore. The study of foreign languages stands out among the priorities of the development of modern education in Uzbekistan. However, achieving a high level of foreign language proficiency is impossible only through classroom lessons without students carrying out independent learning activities. That is why, in order to meet the needs of the digital society in changing learning models and the comprehensive development of the student's personality, one of the options may be the integration of the Flipped Classroom technolo-

gy. The Flipped classroom technology has established itself as a highly effective, innovative and accessible technology for both the teacher and the student in many foreign countries.

We don't notice how fast the modern world is changing. Every second all these changes affect the spheres of human activity in all respects, for example, business, politics, entertainment, etc. To the same extent, the education system is undergoing major changes: the modern image of a high school graduate is completely changing, requirements and standards are increasing. In this regard, there is an urgent need to create and apply new technologies and techniques that correspond to the real-time device, the level and quality of education and life in general.

Unfortunately, in the process of studying how to improve the educational process, difficult questions arise, and choosing the right approach to solving them can increase the effectiveness of training and release "people of renewal" from school, who must be motivated, ambitious, practice-oriented, mobile, people who know the details of social life and own ways to influence the environment. Wednesday. In fact, such a technology already exists, and it is so universal that, for example, at the Clintondale School in the United States of America, education is absolutely completely carried out within the framework of this technology. The technology "inverted classroom - inverted classroom" refers to the research of Harvard Professor Eric Mazur, who created the technology of mutual learning, which became the starting point for the further development of the inverted classroom. Since then, interest in this technology has been growing, and teachers such as John Bergman and Aaron Sams have become one of the most its ideological propagandists.

According to Fischer (2012), learning is no longer split into when and where knowledge is learned and when it is applied. The incorporation of information and communication technologies into the educational process is another sign that encourages blended learning. "ICT integration empowers teachers and students by transforming the process of teaching and learning from a teacher-driven process to a student-centered process," writes Trucano (2005). The technology of the inverted classroom, developed in 2000 by American educators Jonathan Bergman and Aaron Sams, is a major component of blended learning (Bergmann & Sams, 2012).

The objective of this study is to assess the efficacy of implementing flipped-class technologies in the university's educational process. In this article, the inverted classroom technology is going to be studied, and practical experience in implementing this technique in English lessons will be shared. While reviewing the various scientific papers devoted to this concept and its application in the educational process, we discovered that the inverted classroom is defined by Bergmann and Sams (2012) as an educational model in which the elements of the lecture and the course homework are interchangeable. In their book "Flip Your Classroom: Involve Every Student in Every Classroom Every Day," the authors compare the time spent on learning activities in a standard classroom with an inverted classroom. The comparison revealed that in an inverted classroom, practical exercises take up far more time than theoretical information (75 minutes versus 35 minutes).

A group of researchers (Bransford, Brown, & Coking, 2000) discusses the success of the inverted classroom and identifies its important components. According to the authors, mutual assessment allows students to learn fresh knowledge and experience while also improving their grasp of the issue under study. Muldrow (2013) contends in his paper "A New Approach to Language Learning

- an Inverted Classroom" that the move from a standard classroom to an inverted classroom necessitates significant adaptation on the part of both the teacher and the students. Despite numerous studies on flipped classroom instruction, the implementation of this technology in university English classes requires additional research.

The methodology of the study

The study intended to assess the efficacy of flipped classroom technology in the teaching of English at the university level. The following methods were utilized to achieve the research goal: review of scientific literature analysis, study of the use of flipped classroom technology in the educational process, reflection on the authors' own pedagogical experience, and data analysis.

The following research tasks can be distinguished based on the study's purpose:

- 1) Assess the efficacy of the inverted class in English classes.
- 2) familiarize yourself with the concept of “reverse class” technology in the educational process.
- 3) Emphasize the advantages of an inverted class.

The study is based on the scientific works of teachers who have investigated the following issues: the use of information and communication technologies for educational purposes (Kleiman, 2004), the concept of blended learning (Sharma and Barrett, 2007), and the theory and methods of teaching foreign languages (Holmberg et al., 2005).

The concept of “inverted lesson” technology

The technology of the “inverted classroom” refers to the organization of the educational process, in which students already have some theoretical knowledge and understanding of the issue. As a result, students feel more comfortable asking questions and discussing problems with the teacher and their peers, which makes interaction more productive and profitable. In addition, instead of boring presentation of the teacher’s lecture, students are involved in practical activities. As a result, the homework will be unique. Students sometimes suffer from misunderstanding of some questions, assignments and the inability of teachers to get a textbook. As a result, some students prefer to write down the answers to their homework rather than do them in person. In an e-learning environment, students work individually or in groups. They watch video lectures, test their knowledge, solve comprehension questions, and research further learning resources. Students primarily expand the gained material in the classroom by completing practical tasks, developing projects, and discussing various subjects on the topic. Students continue to work with an electronic course after lessons, during which they test their professional knowledge and evaluate the work of their peers. This type of educational process organization reduces the distinction between auditing activities and individual student work. In order for the inverted lesson technology to be successful, all stages of the teaching and learning processes must be integrated and planned.

As the responsibilities of teachers and students change significantly in the inverted lesson, you must now concentrate on the interaction of

participants in the educational process. For starters, on the follow-up lesson, pupils will have the ability to direct their own learning. They learn at their own pace, with all the resources they need in an e-learning environment. Furthermore, students can engage when and where they choose within the time restriction provided for a specific task, they can verify the content at any time if necessary, and they can obtain online support from an instructor or a classmate via chat rooms and forums. Second, Flipped Classroom technology encourages student collaboration through collaborative assignments and group projects. Furthermore, (Marsh 2012) believes that students participate in an expert assessment and provide feedback on the work of their classmates in accordance with the defined criteria, and that collaborative projects force students to collaborate, learn from, and help one another.

Finally, an inverted lesson fosters student ownership of their own learning. They grow more self-sufficient and driven than in regular classrooms. Working with an electronic course and developing self-study abilities teaches students time management. In other words, students' roles in the learning process are evolving, making them active participants in the educational process.

Students participate in a variety of e-learning activities in a flipped classroom. As a result, the teacher's job is to provide a welcoming online atmosphere for students to communicate with one another. The teacher must also be an e-learning facilitator in order to monitor but not direct online exchanges. As a result of the "inverted classroom" technology, the teacher takes on a variety of duties. He or she should encourage and motivate students, supervise and evaluate progress, provide comments, boost confidence, and keep pupils motivated (Marsh, 2012).

Because language acquisition necessitates close interaction between the teacher and pupils, the new roles of the teacher and students are seen especially vital for the process of teaching and learning foreign languages. Based on our pedagogical experience, we would like to point out that students learning English at the Namangan Institute of Foreign Languages have varying English language skills, and hence require varying amounts of time to study theoretical material and complete practical assignments. The "inverted classroom" technology allows students to tack-

le this challenge by allowing them to determine the pace, efficiency, and volume of the content being studied. Furthermore, students' participation in online conversations, forums, and chats helps them build conversational skills, which are critical for language acquisition.

Despite the benefits, as with any novel idea, there are drawbacks that must be overcome in order to successfully integrate flipped classroom technology into the teaching process. One downside is the additional burden that the course instructor imposes when generating the electronic course content. The teacher must devote a significant amount of time, expertise, and effort to recording lectures, generating educational materials, and locating additional resources. If, on the other hand, the e-course is integrated into the educational process, the instructor will have more time for research and methodological work.

Another critical issue is the classroom's and course's electronic components' integrity, which implies that all stages of the educational process and the learning process itself should be logically interrelated. All assignments that students must accomplish within the framework of the e-course must be assessed and evaluated in the classroom or online. No task should be left unconsidered or unevaluated. This increases pupils' drive to study carefully, resulting in a more effective education.

Another downside is that some students are reluctant to swap face-to-face classes in an e-learning environment, afraid that they will "lose" real communication with the teacher and peers. In this scenario, it is vital to explain the concept and specifics of flipped classroom technology to students, as well as show them extra communication tools given by the online course, such as chats, forums, and video conferences.

To meet the study's objectives, the Namangan Institute of Foreign Languages must be guided by the implementation of flipped classroom technology. First-year students were engaged using this technology's approach and studied the English language course. Students attended face-to-face classes, with half of them being replaced with classes in the LMS Google classroom. It is a widely utilized e-learning environment that provides numerous benefits to both teachers and students. The work of the pupils was structured in the classroom and in an e-learning environment. Before full-time sessions, students watched brief video lectures

on the subject of lessons, became acquainted with supplementary online resources, and asked questions for discussion on forums.

The classroom time was spent teaching grammatical and lexical problems, giving presentations and lectures, and debating the most essential concerns. Following the lesson, students evaluated their classmates' work, tested their knowledge of the studied content, and discussed their thoughts on the lesson. All of these endeavors entailed platform work. Assignments were also distributed to pupils via Formative, which served as a positive learning aid.

Discussion

A poll was undertaken to ascertain students' attitudes toward the use of Flipped Classroom technologies for English learning. The idea of incorporating flipped classroom technology into the learning process was liked by 83% of the students who took part in the study. Because of the issues they encountered, 17% of respondents felt uninspired by this technology. Among the challenges were issues with Internet connectivity, a lack of time for online duties, and difficulties with self-discipline when properly arranging their work.

Almost all students (97%) cited the availability of e-learning materials as one of the course's primary benefits. In the e-learning environment, 78% of respondents value the opportunities for collaboration and communication. Teachers mention flexible timetables, integrating students in the learning process, and enhancing student academic achievement as benefits of flipped classroom technology.

Conclusion

Summing up, we can conclude that the reverse class is a promising technology that should not be underestimated. The integration of flipped classroom into the educational process leads to increased motivation and interest of students in learning foreign languages. In addition, it has a positive effect on self-discipline and purposefulness of students. Flipped classroom technology has a huge pedagogical potential for both teachers and students. In addition, the survey results showed that students' academic performance has improved.

In the process of using the “inverted classroom” technology in the educational process, the following advantages were identified:

- convenience (theoretical material is mastered at home in comfortable conditions, or convenience in terms of access to video, that is, there is an opportunity to watch a lecture and complete tasks for it, for example, on a phone, tablet on the way home),
- easy assimilation of the material (consisting in visual perception of the material, as well as in performing tasks while watching the video),
- individual approach (consisting in the fact that you can watch the video lecture repeatedly, at your own pace, as much as you need).

Thus, the prospects of using the technology of the “inverted classroom” is to create an individual and purposeful educational process, without losing the communicative

orientation, teamwork of students and the intensity of the process.

It should be noted that the components that form the basis of the “inverted classroom” technology serve for continuous improvement and exchange of experience in the use of technology between teachers. This feature is a good prospect for the dissemination of this technology, attracting attention to it, as well as the prospect of constant research and study by teachers of any country, which makes it possible to educate their students with the qualities and skills so necessary for a conscious and successful life.

However, there are still some technical and organizational problems that make it difficult to integrate Flipped Classroom technology into the teaching and learning process. Overcoming these problems requires further research to create a new educational environment based on flipped classroom technology.

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